

D3.1: Report on uncertainty quantification methodology

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Abstract:	<p>This deliverable outlines the uncertainty quantification methodology developed in WP3 for key simulation techniques in battery cell manufacturing. The approach systematically categorizes uncertainty sources - method, model, and simulation - and is applied to both molecular dynamics and EOS modeling. Case studies highlight how algorithmic and solver choices affect prediction reliability. The methodology is designed to integrate seamlessly into BatCAT's digital workflow, which connects physical simulations with business decision processes. By combining technical modeling with structured decision-making tools, the framework enables traceable and uncertainty-aware simulations for improved process control in digital twin applications.</p>
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Abbreviations and acronyms

AAD	average absolute deviation
BPMN	business process model and notation
CFD	computational fluid dynamics
DMN	decision model and notation
EMD	equilibrium molecular dynamics
EOS	equation of state
IIDSS	interpretable industrial decision support system
KER	key exploitable result
MCO	multicriteria optimization
MD	molecular dynamics
MoDoD	model-distance-based outlier detection
NEMD	non-equilibrium molecular dynamics
TMWG	technical management working group
UFD	uncertainty flow diagram
UQ	uncertainty quantification

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1. Executive summary

This deliverable presents a comprehensive methodology for the identification and quantification of uncertainties in modeling and simulation of battery manufacturing processes. The concept is generic and can be applied to practically any simulation technique. The objective is to improve the reliability, reproducibility, and transparency of modeling and simulation of battery manufacturing processes. It was tested and validated using two specific simulation techniques, namely molecular simulation using classical force fields and equations of state (EOS). The report covers a description of the developed uncertainty quantification methodology – first giving an overview; then, giving details and demonstrating the application to exemplary modeling techniques. These two examples differ significantly demonstrating the robustness of the uncertainty quantification methodology. In the second part of the BatCAT project, we will apply the novel uncertainty quantification methodology to battery manufacturing use cases.

The increasing complexity of digital manufacturing processes, combined with the integration of models, simulations, and experimental data, necessitates a rigorous approach to uncertainty quantification (UQ) and reliability assessment. Uncertainty Quantification (UQ) is a cornerstone of the BatCAT project's strategy to develop reliable, transparent, and actionable digital twins for battery cell manufacturing. D3.1 addresses this challenge by developing a formal methodology for the representation, propagation, and management of uncertainty across the manufacturing data space and supporting provenance tracking. The objectives of the deliverable D3.1 is to:

- Develop a **formal model** and methodology for representing uncertainty and reliability.
- Establish mechanisms for **uncertainty propagation**.
- Support **evidence aggregation** from heterogeneous sources.
- Enable **documentation** of uncertainties in models, simulations, and experimental data.

2. Progress report (main activities)

2.1. *Overview of uncertainty quantification methodology*

In BatCAT, a formal methodology for uncertainty quantification has been developed as a key exploitable result (KER). This methodology is a core component of Work Package 3 (Interoperability Infrastructure), specifically Task 3.4. The focus was on the uncertainty quantification of modeling and simulation techniques used for battery production modeling. Yet, also experimental data uncertainty was incorporated in the developed uncertainty quantification methodology.

We have developed a comprehensive methodology for the identification and quantification of uncertainties across different modeling and simulation techniques. The methodology is built as a

hierarchical concept, i.e. has three main elements. Thus, the uncertainties of battery manufacturing digital twins can be broadly classified into three overarching categories (see also Fig. 1):

- **Method Uncertainty:** Each modeling and simulation method (could also be experimental method), inherently carries its own uncertainty. These uncertainties are a result of the basic assumptions and simplifications of the method. Depending on their assumptions and complexity, models approximate physical phenomena to different degrees of accuracy, resulting in uncertainties of the digital twin with regard to reality, e.g. the simplifications of classical molecular dynamics simulations where Newtonian mechanics are used. Another example could be simplifications of a macroscopic computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulation, e.g. regarding the turbulence model and which balance equations are considered in the method.
- **Model Uncertainty:** For a given method, a specific model has to be employed for the execution of a simulation, e.g. a specific model for a given substance and its thermophysical properties. A specific model consists usually of a mathematical backbone and its parameters. The model parameters were usually trained to some experimental data at some point. A given model will reflect reality only to a certain degree and, during the parameter adjustment, choices were made which aspects are very accurate captured by the model and which other aspects only moderately accurately – knowing that compromises have to be made for practically all models. For example, a specific force field has to be used in a classical molecular dynamics simulation that comprises specific model parameters that were adjusted to viscosity and gas solubility data. Thus, using the same method, different models can lead to varying outcomes.
- **Simulation Uncertainty:** During the execution of a simulation (or experiment), additional uncertainties arise. This includes statistical uncertainty – stemming from randomness or chaotic system behavior – as well as systematic uncertainty, which can be introduced through algorithmic implementation, numerical settings, or software-specific behavior.

Figure 1: Overview of uncertainty quantification methodology for modelling and simulation of battery manufacturing processes.

These categories form the conceptual basis for our uncertainty quantification methodology. Behind each category, variables (at least one for each category) exist which actually quantify the uncertainty. The sum of these uncertainties quantifies the deviation of the battery manufacturing digital twin to the real-world manufacturing process.

We have applied and tested this methodology to multiple modeling and simulation steps and aspects of battery manufacturing. Several outcomes have already been published, including eight peer-reviewed articles [Fer24, Ren24a, Ren24b, Sch24a, Sch24c, Sta24, Sta25, Ste24] and two articles [Hor24a, Hor24b] conducted in collaboration with BatCAT contributors. We have applied the uncertainty quantification methodology in the context of equations of state that were used for modeling thermophysical properties of fluids relevant for battery manufacturing. Moreover, we have applied the uncertainty quantification methodology to molecular dynamics simulations for battery cell manufacturing processes. Our work has focused on assessing and reducing method uncertainty, model uncertainty, and simulation uncertainty.

Additionally, the methodology was developed incorporating various aspects and contributions from different BatCAT consortium partners, namely:

- **Formal Model Development:** A formal model for uncertainty and reliability was developed. This development was coordinated with the semantics defined in Task 4.4, which focuses on metadata standardization and ontologies. This ensures that uncertainty is consistently represented across the knowledge base.
- **Uncertainty Propagation:** The methodology was applied to uncertainty propagation across different stages of the process, notably over Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN). This is crucial for understanding how uncertainties accumulate and impact downstream steps in the battery manufacturing process. The real-time functionality will also implement uncertainty propagation/explainability based on surrogate models.
- **Evidence Aggregation:** Formal methods were developed for aggregating and combining evidence. This is essential for synthesizing information from diverse sources (e.g., experimental data, multiphysics simulations, data-driven models) while accounting for their inherent uncertainties.
- **Integration with Provenance Tracking:** The uncertainty quantification methodology was integrated into the provenance tracking system across the BatCAT data space. This linkage ensures that the origin and transformations of data are documented, allowing users to trace back the source of uncertainty and verify the lineage of results.
- **Input for Industrial Decision Support:** The Interpretable Industrial Decision Support System (IIDSS) provides explainable measures for uncertainty quantification and its propagation. This means that the system does not just offer recommendations but also clarify the level of confidence or uncertainty associated with those recommendations, empowering informed human decision-making.
- **MCO Integration:** The MCO (Multicriteria Optimization) methodology from ITWM, a core component of the IIDSS, is designed to provide reliable and self-documenting (explainable) metrics for uncertainty quantification and propagation during model parameterization.

These efforts directly support the development of digital twin applications in battery manufacturing, where predictive models must be accurate, reproducible, and transparent to enable reliable process design, optimization, and control. Our uncertainty quantification methodology spans the entire simulation workflow: from data-driven parameter fitting to the propagation of uncertainty in multiscale modeling. By establishing protocols for model calibration, experimental data selection, and the systematic characterization of statistical and systematic uncertainties, we provide a robust framework for integrating different levels of uncertainties of modeling and simulation in battery manufacturing. This provides a robust and widely applicable framework.

In the following sections, results from individual aspects of the uncertainty quantification methodology are reported illustrating the robustness and general applicability of the approach. In total, three examples were studied exemplifying the general applicability of the uncertainty quantification framework.

The first application example of our uncertainty quantification methodology focuses on the prediction of thermophysical properties using EOS, which are essential for modeling complex fluid behavior under conditions encountered in battery manufacturing processes. In this context, EOS frameworks such as PC-SAFT and SAFT-VR Mie were employed to compute key properties including phase equilibria, density, enthalpy, and the heat capacity of solvents.

These EOS models are based on the Helmholtz energy formalism, which is decomposed into two components: the intramolecular (id) contribution, representing energy stored within intramolecular degrees of freedom, and the residual (res) contribution, which accounts for intermolecular interactions. These models are formulated as a function of temperature and density, i.e.

$$a(T, \rho) = a^{\text{id}}(T, \rho) + a^{\text{res}}(T, \rho)$$

While the residual part is typically calibrated using experimental data, the id contribution must be supplied separately to ensure accurate caloric property predictions, which is for example critical for accurately describing the drying of the slurry in the digital twin. This is also highly relevant in battery manufacturing, where thermophysical properties such as isobaric heat capacity c_p are critical for designing energy-efficient drying and solvent removal steps.

All three uncertainty categories (cf. Fig. 1) were studied for EOS models, namely the method uncertainties, the model uncertainties, and the simulation uncertainties. The results are reported below in detail.

In the second example molecular dynamics simulations for the prediction of transport properties relevant for battery manufacturing were considered. In this example, the method uncertainties as well as the simulation uncertainties were studied.

As EOS are deterministic, statistical uncertainties are not a concern mostly; However, systematic simulation uncertainties are relevant and were studied here as an example. Moreover, the method uncertainty of EOS models was evaluated. Also, the model uncertainty of different EOS models was evaluated. This gives insights in the relations of the three main uncertainty categories within a single

simulation method. For molecular dynamics simulations, our focus has been on the systematic simulation (i.e. execution-based) uncertainty as well as statistical simulation uncertainty, particularly in quantifying statistical variability and identifying sources of systematic deviation across different simulation engines and calculation methods for the prediction of transport properties for battery manufacturing processes.

In the third example, Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) were studied and specifically how the different uncertainties accumulate and propagate therein.

This gives comprehensive insights in the applicability of the developed uncertainty quantification methodology.

2.2. Model uncertainty of EOS models

The model uncertainty of EOS models was evaluated using a rigorous and large-scale parametrization approach for EOS models relevant for battery manufacturing processes, e.g. lubricant fluids, cleaning solvent fluids, electrolyte fluids etc. Therefore, we developed an algorithm that conducted a large-scale parameterization effort involving over 705,000 experimental data points for 2,426 distinct substances. This comprehensive dataset includes the saturated densities, vapor pressure, enthalpy of vaporization, density, heat capacity, and speed of sound, enabling robust optimization of model parameters. The selection and quality of experimental data are recognized as key factors influencing the accuracy of molecular-based EOS predictions. Therefore, we implemented a model-distance-based outlier detection (MoDOD) algorithm [Sch24b] that automates the identification of inconsistent or erroneous data points. This method quantifies deviations between model predictions and data subsets and facilitates robust regression without the need for manual data curation.

The entire pipeline (cf. Fig. 2), from data retrieval to parameter optimization, requires only a CAS number and EOS selection as input. It proceeds autonomously, significantly reducing human-induced variability and ensuring reproducibility. Importantly, in contrast to many existing parameterization approaches, we explicitly incorporate the id contributions based on quantum mechanical data such that also information on the uncertainty introduced by coupling is incorporated in the uncertainty quantification method.

The optimized parameters include chain length m , segment size σ , and dispersion energy ε for PC-SAFT, with additional parameters for SAFT-VR Mie describing the repulsive exponent λ_R and, in the case of associating fluids, the association energy ε_{AB} and volume κ_{AB} . Moreover, the resulting parameter sets are made available through the MolMod database [Ste19], enhancing accessibility for use in further modeling workflows, including digital twin environments.

Figure 2: Flowchart for the algorithm for assessing the model uncertainty of EOS models for battery manufacturing. The algorithm carries out automatic fitting of substance specific parameters of molecular-based EOS models to experimental data and compares the results.

The accuracy and reliability of the fitted EOS models were evaluated using a range of statistical metrics, with particular emphasis on the average absolute deviation (AAD) across various thermophysical properties, as shown in Fig. 3. Among these, phase equilibrium properties are especially informative for model assessment, as they are highly sensitive to molecular interactions, extensively documented in experimental literature, and provide a rigorous benchmark for thermodynamic consistency across phases. Based on the VLE analysis, the SAFT-VR Mie EOS achieved a mean AAD of 0.62% for saturated liquid density, slightly outperforming PC-SAFT. For isochoric heat capacity, both EOS frameworks delivered similarly strong performance, confirming their suitability for predicting thermal behavior relevant to battery production processes. Moreover, specific values for the model uncertainty of different EOS models have now become available.

Figure 3: Box plot of the AAD for the phase equilibrium properties saturated liquid density ρ' , saturated gas density ρ'' , vapor pressure p^s , enthalpy of vaporization Δh_v , density ρ , isobaric heat capacity c_p , isochoric heat capacity c_v and speed of sound w . Both the lower quartile Q1 and the upper quartile Q3, as well as the 1.5-fold interquartile range (IQR) are given. The median and mean are also shown. The results of the SAFT-VR Mie are shown in red and the results of the PC-SAFT in blue.

To further explore the phase-specific performance of the models, we analyzed the prediction of the speed of sound across different thermodynamic states as shown in Fig.4, including the saturated liquid and vapor phases, subcooled liquids, and the supercritical region. Results show that SAFT-VR Mie consistently outperforms PC-SAFT in predicting the speed of sound in the liquid phase, while PC-SAFT exhibits slight advantages in the vapor and supercritical domains. These findings highlight the necessity of phase-specific evaluation when assessing uncertainty and selecting models for integration into process simulations. Moreover, the model uncertainty of PC-SAFT significantly exceed those from the SAFT-VR Mie model making the latter the preferable choice one for battery manufacturing modeling.

Figure 4: Box plot of the AAD for the properties speed of sound in the liquid phase w' , speed of sound in the vapor phase w'' , speed of sound in the liquid region w^L , speed of sound in the gaseous region w^V and speed of sound in the supercritical region w^{SCT} . Both the lower quartile Q1 and the upper quartile Q3, as well as the 1.5-fold interquartile range (IQR) are given. The median and mean are also shown. The results of the SAFT-VR Mie are shown in red and the results of the PC-SAFT in blue.

2.3. Method uncertainty of id EOS contribution

For the accurate modeling of caloric fluid properties in battery manufacturing, an id EOS model for the intramolecular energy storage is required. Since no such model was available with a sufficient accuracy, a new model was developed within this work. For this new id EOS model, the method uncertainty was critically assessed. The results are reported in the following.

A key challenge in this area arises from the lack of reliable id EOS models for many parametrized molecules. This limitation can compromise the predictive accuracy of caloric properties, introducing uncertainty into thermal simulations used in digital twins of battery processes. To address this issue, we have developed a systematic and scalable multi-scale and multi-physics approach to modeling the intramolecular Helmholtz energy contribution, which is described in more detail below.

Reliable predictions of caloric properties such as heat capacities are essential for the thermal management of battery production steps, including electrode drying and solvent evaporation. In many EOS formulations, the id contribution is either neglected or treated using rough approximations, leading to notable uncertainties in predicted properties. Here, a new model was developed with significantly lower method uncertainties, which is at the same time widely applicable.

To overcome this issue, we have developed a framework for calculating the id Helmholtz energy contribution using first-principle quantum mechanics methods. This model is built upon statistical mechanics and incorporates quantum mechanical simulation results of molecular vibrational and rotational energy levels. High-throughput calculations were performed for more than 20,000

substances, and the resulting data were used to construct molecular partition functions without any empirical fitting. This provides a powerful model for describing caloric properties of fluids in battery manufacturing processes.

For model validation and assessment of the method uncertainty, we evaluated the AAD across different substance groups using literature data for isobaric heat capacities of approximately 1,000 molecules. The dataset was categorized by functional groups to assess performance across diverse chemistries. The mean deviations ranged from 0.5% to 8%, with over 91% of the predictions falling within a 5% error margin. The results are summarized in Fig. 5. This high level of accuracy, achieved without any adjustable parameters, demonstrates the robustness and transferability of the model, making it well-suited for uncertainty-aware thermodynamic modeling. In particular, the uncertainty of the method is known, which makes its application reliable and transparent.

Figure 5: Box plot of the AAD for the id EOS isobaric heat capacity $c_{p,intra}$. Both the lower quartile $Q1$ and the upper quartile $Q3$, as well as 1.5-fold interquartile range IQR are given.

From perspective of battery production process, this model substantially reduces the uncertainty in thermal process simulations, thereby improving the reliability of predictions in critical steps such as thermal ramping and in situ drying. Its integration with EOS frameworks like PC-SAFT and SAFT-VR Mie allows for fully consistent thermodynamic modeling with *quantified uncertainty bounds* within the newly developed uncertainty quantification framework.

2.4. Systematic simulation uncertainties and statistical simulation uncertainties in molecular dynamics simulations

While statistical uncertainty is a well-recognized aspect of molecular dynamics (MD) simulations, the role of systematic uncertainty is often underestimated. However, consistent deviations arising from differences in simulation engines, algorithmic implementations, and user-defined parameters can significantly impact predictive accuracy. This is especially critical in multiscale modeling workflows, where the reliable prediction of substance properties at the fundamental level is essential to ensure the physical meaningfulness of the simulations.

To systematically assess implementation-related systematic simulation uncertainties, we conducted a cross-code benchmarking study using five widely adopted simulation engines - ms2, GROMACS, LAMMPS, DL_POLY, and MDynaMix - and three transport property methods: Green-Kubo, Einstein relations, and gradient-based techniques. Simulations were performed for a model fluid, applying both equilibrium (EMD) and non-equilibrium (NEMD) approaches to compute self-diffusion, shear viscosity, and thermal conductivity. A common set of tasks and baseline settings was provided to all participants, though not all methods were applicable to every task.

Figure 6: Flow chart of the procedure for determining the systematic simulation uncertainty of MD simulations: Task definition for all simulation codes, individual work using different codes and methods, comparison and evaluation of the results.

A key element of our uncertainty quantification methodology is the systematic documentation of simulation conditions that affect reproducibility and comparability. Rather than relying solely on the concept of metadata in a narrow technical sense, the methodology emphasizes the importance of recording all relevant aspects of a simulation setup that contribute to statistical and systematic simulation uncertainties. This includes:

- Algorithmic choices, such as thermostats and integration schemes,
- Numerical settings, including timestep size, cutoff distances, and convergence thresholds,

- Hardware and software environments, including compiler settings or parallelization strategies.

Capturing this information in a structured and transparent manner enables traceable simulation workflows and more meaningful comparisons across different simulation tools, methods, and research groups. This becomes especially important when simulation results are used to inform process-level models in battery manufacturing, where uncertainty in input data can directly affect decision-making.

From a practical standpoint, particularly in applied production scenarios, systematic simulation uncertainties cannot be fully avoided, but they can be identified and mitigated through careful analysis. For example, in Fig. 7, in our cross-code benchmark study of a model fluid, predictions of shear viscosity at a selected state point, where we compared results from multiple methods. The systematic simulation uncertainty was estimated to be approximately 5.5%, while the average statistical simulation uncertainty across all data points was around 4%. Notably, not all results agreed within their statistical error bounds, and one data point deviated beyond the combined statistical and systematic uncertainty, indicating a likely implementation-specific inconsistency. These findings underscore the importance of uncertainty documentation and method comparison in achieving reliable and reproducible simulation results. Moreover, these results underline the importance of considering both the statistical as well as the systematic simulation uncertainties in modeling and simulation of battery manufacturing processes.

Figure 7: Comparison of shear viscosity predictions across different methods, highlighting associated statistical and systematic simulation uncertainties.

Our benchmarking results reveal that the variability between different MD codes and predictions often exceeds the statistical uncertainties reported for individual simulations. These discrepancies arise from factors such as algorithmic implementation, numerical settings, and user decisions, even when simulations are performed under nominally identical conditions. Such variability provides a valuable benchmark for evaluating the robustness of simulation engines and methods, and it highlights the need for deeper understanding of systematic sources of error in routine workflows.

Despite the growing maturity of molecular simulation techniques, reproducibility in this domain remains limited. The effects of software choices, hardware platforms, and user-defined configurations are still not well characterized, and their impact on the reliability of predicted

properties can be substantial. Developing practical strategies to estimate and reduce these systematic uncertainties requires transparent documentation of simulation conditions and method-specific influences. This work contributes to making MD simulations more transparent and reliable – especially for battery manufacturing modeling.

By identifying and addressing the sources of systematic simulation uncertainties, we not only enhance the credibility of molecular simulation results, but also enable their confident use in digital twin applications for battery manufacturing. Here, accurate and reproducible molecular-level data are essential for predicting macroscopic behavior, guiding process optimization, and informing real-time control strategies. Robust uncertainty quantification thus plays a foundational role in bridging simulation outputs with actionable insights in battery production.

2.5. *Systematic simulation uncertainties in EOS modeling*

Equations of state (EOS) offer an efficient and practical alternative to classical molecular simulations for the prediction of fluid thermophysical properties in battery manufacturing processes. Moreover, they can be favorably used for scale bridging and multi-physics simulation coupling. These models, e.g. PC-SAFT or SAFT-VR Mie, provide fast and scalable computations, making them highly suitable for integration into multiscale simulation of battery manufacturing processes, where rapid evaluation of thermodynamic properties is required. However, despite their computational advantages, EOS models are subject to their own sources of uncertainty, which must be properly understood and quantified to ensure reliable predictions.

Unlike molecular simulations, molecular-based EOS do not exhibit statistical uncertainty in the traditional sense, as their predictions are deterministic once the model and parameters are defined. Nevertheless, systematic uncertainties can still arise from various factors, particularly those related to the numerical implementation of the EOS and the algorithms used for property calculation. In addition to the method uncertainties and model uncertainties of EOS, which were addressed in detail in previous sections, these implementation-related differences lead to systematic simulation uncertainties of the predicted properties.

To systematically assess these uncertainties, we conducted a comprehensive benchmarking study involving multiple software tools and EOS formulations. The objective was to quantify the systematic simulation uncertainties in EOS predictions, i.e. uncertainties resulting from the actual execution, stemming from differences in software implementation, computational algorithms, and numerical methods. This study covered a broad spectrum of thermodynamic properties, including homogeneous state points, critical point estimations, pure-component and binary mixture phase equilibria. These tasks represent key thermodynamic conditions commonly encountered in modelling fluid behavior during battery production processes, such as electrolyte mixing, gas-liquid phase transitions, and solvent separation.

The benchmarking was carried out across eleven different EOS software implementations: AspenPlus v12, Clapeyron, CoolProp, FEOS, MicTherm, phasepy, REFPROP, TEQP, ThermoC, ThermoPack, and TREND. Each of these software environments supports various EOS models, including both classical

cubic equations (e.g., Peng-Robinson, PSRK, VTPR) and more advanced molecular-based formulations (e.g., GERG-2008, PeTS, PC-SAFT, PCP-SAFT, SAFT-VR Mie).

To ensure a meaningful cross-comparison, we selected a representative set of fluids: cyclohexane, carbon dioxide, methanol, acetone, methane, and argon, that span a broad range of molecular complexities and interaction types. Several of these substances are somewhere involved in battery production processes, e.g. as cleaning agent and gas in the environment. This makes them ideal candidates for benchmarking the consistency, accuracy, and implementation fidelity of different EOS software tools, i.e. determining systematic simulation uncertainties. The insights derived from these comparisons establish a robust methodological foundation, which can be extended to other battery-relevant systems involving complex polar solvents and electrolyte mixtures. Such transferability is essential for enabling reliable EOS integration into digital twin frameworks supporting battery manufacturing and process optimization.

Before comparing the accuracy of predictions across different software platforms and the resulting systematic simulation uncertainty, it is important to recognize that each implementation of an EOS is subject to inherent limitations regarding the range of supported equations of state and the availability of thermodynamic properties for specific substances. These constraints influence not only the types of calculations that can be performed but also the fidelity of the results produced. A comparison of the available models and property calculation capabilities across the different software tools is illustrated in Fig. 8.

Figure 8: Overview of EOS and task availability across the evaluated software tools for EOS modelling for determining their systematic simulation uncertainty.

Initial results from our benchmarking study revealed noticeable discrepancies between implementations and therefore significant systematic simulation uncertainties - especially for more complex models such as PC-SAFT. These inconsistencies are exemplified by deviations in the predicted speed of sound for carbon dioxide as illustrated in Fig. 9, where the results varied significantly depending on the software used, i.e. significant systematic simulation uncertainties.

Figure 9: Relative deviation (corresponding to systematic simulation uncertainties) in the predicted thermodynamic property of carbon dioxide calculated using different software implementations. Identical parameters and state points were applied across all tools. Two different EOS models were evaluated: (left) the cubic Peng–Robinson EOS, and (right) the molecular-based PC-SAFT EOS. The baseline for comparison is the median value of all results.

Similar deviations were observed for other key thermodynamic properties, such as vapor pressure and enthalpy of vaporization – see Fig. 10. In this case, the property values of methanol were directly calculated as a function of temperature using the SAFT-VR Mie EOS by different software implementations. The results, presented in the diagram below, clearly demonstrate the presence of significant systematic simulation uncertainties. These are isolated systematic simulation uncertainties.

Figure 10: Systematic simulation uncertainties obtained for the vapor pressure (left) and enthalpy of vaporization (right) of methanol as calculated using the SAFT-VR Mie EOS. Results from different software implementations are distinguished by color.

These findings underscore the importance of accounting for implementation-specific uncertainties, i.e. systematic simulation uncertainties, when applying EOS in multiscale simulation frameworks for battery manufacturing. Even small differences in property predictions at the thermodynamic level can propagate through coupled models - impacting, for example, thermal management strategies or solvent evaporation simulations in battery production workflows. This is particularly relevant for digital twins, where accuracy and consistency across all modeling layers are essential for meaningful prediction and control.

In conclusion, while EOS provide substantial advantages in terms of computational efficiency and scalability compared to molecular simulations, their deterministic nature does not guarantee consistency across different implementations. Thus, significant systematic simulation uncertainties are present in both (and also in other) simulation techniques. As a result, benchmarking systematic simulation uncertainties are now available. Transparent documentation of algorithmic details are vital to reduce systematic simulation uncertainties for ensuring that these models can be reliably used in the development and deployment of digital twins for battery manufacturing.

Both molecular simulation and EOS approaches are particularly important in the context of digital twin applications for battery manufacturing, where predictive models at the molecular level serve as the foundation for capturing macroscopic behavior and supporting real-time process control. While molecular simulations offer detailed insights into microscopic interactions, EOS provide a computationally efficient means of extending these insights to broader thermodynamic conditions and process-relevant time scales. Accurate and reproducible data from both modeling strategies are essential to ensure that the digital twin reliably reflects the physical system. In this context, structured metadata plays a critical role by providing the transparency, consistency, and traceability needed to quantify uncertainties and ensure the credibility of multiscale simulations. These two simulation techniques were used to illustrate the general applicability of the developed uncertainty quantification methodology.

2.6. Method and model uncertainties in BPMN and DMN

Battery manufacturing involves complex workflows that span physical, chemical, and operational domains. To achieve high efficiency and quality, it is essential to bridge the gap between technical processes and business logic. BatCAT introduces a unified modeling approach using BPMN (Business Process Model and Notation), DMN (Decision Model and Notation), and a novel construct Uncertainty Flow Diagrams (UFDs) to support uncertainty aware decision-making in battery production.

BPMN provides a graphical representation of workflows with tasks, events, and decision gateways. BatCAT uses BPMN to represent tasks at multiple levels:

- Macro-level: Entire production lines.
- Meso-level: Machine- or process-specific flows.
- Micro-level: Operator interactions.

DMN rules define the business decisions that guide task execution. Examples include:

- Batteries classification based on test results.
- Process parameter selection.
- Re-routing of out-of-spec batches.

BPMN and DMN do not natively model uncertainty. Key limitations include:

- Inability to capture statistical or epistemic uncertainty.
- Lack of traceable uncertainty propagation.
- Difficulty in integrating simulation uncertainty.

Figure 11: Overview of the envisaged solution showing the steps of design, specification, translation, and analysis [Cam24].

Fig. 11 illustrates the methodological context of the UFD approach. This approach is primarily intended for engineers building adaptive systems and is designed to be used at the design stage. The core purpose of this methodology, as depicted in Fig. 11, is to take existing design and implementation artefacts as input and produce a report detailing the impact of UPI on key system properties. This output report is crucial for enabling engineers to make informed decisions regarding necessary design and implementation adjustments to mitigate the effects of UPI on the system's properties and goals. The process itself is iterative, allowing for the incremental refinement of the system's design and implementation. The methodology presented in Fig. 11 comprises the following distinct steps:

- **S0. Design & implementation:**
 - This initial stage precedes the rest of the process if the necessary set of design and implementation artefacts is not already available at the outset.
 - It represents the foundational work from which the subsequent analytical steps build upon.
- **S1a. UFD specification:**
 - This step involves engineers actively constructing UFDs.
 - The construction of these diagrams is informed by existing system artefacts and the knowledge of stakeholders, such as members of the engineering team or domain experts.
- **S1b. Requirements formalisation:**
 - Concurrently with UFD specification, this step focuses on the formalisation of system requirements.
 - These requirements can encompass various aspects, including constraints (e.g. quality-related), system goals, and other pertinent system properties.
- **S2. Translation:**
 - Following the specification of UFDs, this stage involves the translation of the UFDs into formal specifications.
 - These formal specifications then serve as the input for the tools that will be utilised in the subsequent propagation analysis step.
- **S3. Propagation analysis:**
 - This is the final analytical step, where propagation analysis is conducted using formal analysis tools.
 - The outcome of this analysis provides results that inform how various uncertainties interact and, consequently, how they affect the set of system properties that were formalised in step S1b.

UFDs overlay BPMN to explicitly represent uncertainty:

- Each BPMN task maps to a UFD action.
- UFD actions include metadata for input, process, and output uncertainty.

UFDs allow:

- Traceable uncertainty propagation through workflows.

- Task-level risk estimation.
- Dynamic adaptation of decisions using DMN.

This enables a closed-loop system:

- Simulations/data provide quantified uncertainties.
- UFDs translate these into workflow uncertainty contexts.
- DMN rules adapt operations accordingly.

The architecture is structured as follows:

Simulation + Data Analytics → Uncertainty Quantification → UFDs → BPMN Tasks → DMN Decisions

This flow ensures that operational decisions are informed by scientific insights and quantified risks.

3. Conclusions

In this work, we have established a comprehensive methodology for uncertainty quantification. We have applied and tested this methodology in different simulation techniques, e.g. molecular dynamics simulations and EOS modeling, with a focus on specific applications in battery production and digital twin environments. Here, examples were chosen from the modeling of fluid properties in battery cell manufacturing processes. The uncertainty quantification methodology rigorously categorizes different and independent uncertainty sources, namely method uncertainties, model uncertainties, and simulation uncertainties. The latter were sub-divided into systematic simulation uncertainties and statistical simulation uncertainties. This framework enables a comprehensive coverage of different and diverse effects causing deviations from predictions of a battery cell manufacturing digital twin from a real process.

We systematically tested this methodology using several examples. The results did not only confirm the applicability of the uncertainty quantification methodology, but also provide novel insights in the applicability and reliability of specific modeling and simulation techniques for battery manufacturing modeling. On the one hand, molecular dynamics simulations provide detailed, bottom-up insight into the behavior of fluids and materials in battery cell manufacturing, but are inherently subject to statistical noise and sensitivity to simulation protocols. We systematically examined how different algorithms, sampling methods, and software engines influence systematic simulation uncertainties of key transport properties. To improve transparency and traceability, we emphasized the importance of structured metadata to capture simulation details, numerical settings, and sources of error, enabling more consistent and comparable computational experiments. On the other hand, EOS models, such as PC-SAFT and SAFT-VR Mie, offer deterministic and efficient tools for predicting thermodynamic properties over wide ranges of temperature, pressure, and composition relevant for battery cell manufacturing. Through large-scale data-driven parameterization and benchmarking

studies, we demonstrated how differences in EOS implementation and solver algorithms can lead to considerable discrepancies, even when using the same theoretical model and substance parameters. Thereby, both model and method uncertainties were individually quantified. These findings highlight the necessity of implementation-sensitive uncertainty evaluation, especially when these models are embedded in higher-level process simulations.

BatCAT's integrated use of BPMN, DMN, and UFDs enables seamless coordination of physical and business models in battery manufacturing. UFDs provide a formal mechanism to represent and propagate uncertainty, allowing for risk-aware process control and optimization. This integration closes the loop between simulations, real-world operations, and decision-making.

We will employ the developed uncertainty quantification methodology in different multi-physics simulation techniques for specific battery cell manufacturing process simulations in the second part of the BatCAT project. Moreover, the results on the uncertainty quantification methodology will be disseminated appropriately.

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Appendix: Key concepts for uncertainty metadata standardization

Our recommendation is to use the PTB's formalization of uncertainty, as standardized in its metadata standard D-SI, which is already taken over in the Metadata4Ing ontology.

Sources:

- D-SI (from PTB, Braunschweig)
- Metadata4Ing (from NFDI4Ing)
- MSO-EM (mid-level ontologies developed in BatCAT, see e.g. [Hor24a, Hor24b, Hor25])
- PIMS-II (previous work underlying to MSO-EM)

Key concept:

- **uncertainty declaration**
 - Definition: Articulation applied to a **numerical variable** to give an assessment of its uncertainty
 - Scope note: e.g., a **coverage interval** or an **expanded uncertainty**
 - Scope note: Uncertainty declaration is the domain of the relations **has coverage probability** (range: literal) and **has statistical distribution** (range: **statistical distribution**)

Concepts associated with the key concept (all from D-SI, Metadata4Ing, PIMS-II):

- **assignment**

- Definition: Equality articulation by which a **value** is **assigned to** a **variable** with respect to a particular referent
- Example: T = 200 K for substance o as it was measured in a particular cognitive step); T is the **variable**, 200 K is the **value**, and o is the referent.
- Rule: **assigns** some **value**
- Rule: **assigns to** some **variable**
- Rule: *has referent* some *thing* (owl:Thing)
- **coverage interval**
 - Definition: Articulation of a probabilistic-symmetric coverage interval for a real uncertainty
 - Rule: **has coverage probability** some *literal* (rdfs:Literal)
 - Rule: **has interval maximum** some *literal*
 - Rule: **has interval minimum** some *literal*
 - Rule: **has standard uncertainty** some *literal*
- **expanded uncertainty**
 - Definition: Articulation of an expanded measurement, model, or simulation uncertainty
 - Rule: **has coverage factor** some *literal*
 - "Coverage factor: Numerical factor used as a multiplier of the combined standard uncertainty in order to obtain an expanded uncertainty" (JCGM 100:2008)
 - Rule: **has coverage probability** some *literal*
 - Rule: **has uncertainty** some *literal*
- **number**
 - Definition: Lexeme that is numerical in nature
 - Rule: *is literally* some *literal*
- **numerical variable**
 - Definition: Variable that expects a floating point or integer value
 - Scope note: A **numerical variable** can have an **uncertainty declaration**; a *real* (subclass of **numerical variable**) requires an **uncertainty declaration**.
- **property**
 - Definition: **Variable** employed for the possible outcome of observations
- **quantity value**
 - Rule: *has magnitude* some *number*
 - Rule: *has unit* some *measurement unit*
- **real**
 - Definition: **Numerical variable** with a measurement unit and an uncertainty declaration
 - Rule: **has uncertainty declaration** some **uncertainty declaration**
- **statistical distribution**
 - Definition: Probability distribution type (*e.g.*, normal distribution) associated with the **value** of a **variable** through the variable's **uncertainty declaration**
- **value**
 - Rule: *is admissible for* some **variable**
- **variable**
 - Definition: Conventional that is employed for something to which values can be assigned